

IMPERATIVE SENTENCE IN “CALL OF DUTY BLACK OPS 6 CAMPAIGN”

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ABSTRACT

The aims of this study is to find out the types of imperative sentence Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign. The theory used in this research is theory proposed by Quirk et. al. (1985) in their book entitled A Comprehensive of English Language about types of imperative sentence which consist five types of imperative sentence in this research, there are Imperative without subject, imperative with subject, imperative with let, Negative imperative and imperative with do, and to determine the constituent structure by using tree diagram based on the theory proposed by Brown and Miller (1991). The result of the data was presented in formal method of finding presentation. The formal method was applied through table and tree diagram and the informal method was applied through word explanation to explain the constituent structure of imperative sentence. The result of this study showed there are 401 sentences categorized into types of imperative sentence, there were 4 types of imperative sentence found, such as 272 (67.83%) imperative without subject, 58 (14.46%) imperative with subject, 42 (10.47%) imperative with let, and 29 (7.23%) negative imperative and imperative with do.

Keywords: *imperative sentence, types, constituent structure*

ABSTRAK

Tujuan dari penelitian ini adalah untuk mengetahui jenis kalimat imperatif Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign. Teori yang digunakan dalam penelitian ini adalah teori yang dikemukakan oleh Quirk et. Al. (1985) dalam bukunya yang berjudul A Comprehensive of English Language tentang jenis-jenis kalimat imperatif yang terdiri dari lima jenis kalimat imperatif dalam penelitian ini, yaitu Imperatif tanpa subjek, imperatif dengan subjek, imperatif dengan let, imperatif negatif, dan imperatif dengan do, dan untuk menentukan struktur penyusunnya dengan menggunakan diagram pohon berdasarkan teori yang dikemukakan oleh Brown dan Miller (1991). Hasil data disajikan dalam metode formal presentasi temuan. Metode formal diterapkan melalui tabel dan diagram pohon dan metode informal diterapkan melalui penjelasan kata untuk menjelaskan struktur penyusun kalimat imperatif. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan terdapat 401 kalimat yang dikategorikan ke dalam jenis kalimat imperatif, terdapat 4 jenis kalimat imperatif yang ditemukan, yaitu 272 (67,83%) kalimat imperatif tanpa subjek, 58 (14,46%) kalimat imperatif dengan subjek, 42 (10,47%) imperatif dengan let, dan 29 (7,23%) imperatif negatif dengan do.

Kata Kunci: *kalimat imperatif, tipe – tipe, struktur konstituen*

Introduction

Language has an important role in communication. Through language people can communicate to each other and express everything in their minds. Since English is the international language, English plays an important role in the world. It is used by many people around the world in all aspect of their life either spoken or written. It's interesting to analyze English language used in written text because it is in the form of sentences with elaborate structure. In English there are four types of sentences those are declarative, interrogative, imperative and exclamative sentence, each of the sentence type has its own characteristic and language function (Quirk et al., 1973:191).

Imperative sentence it has various forms and it is often used in our daily life, especially in conversation. According to Quirk et al (1985:803), that stated in their book entitled A Comprehensive Grammar of The English Language, imperative sentence is a sentence which normally does not have grammatical subject, and the verb base form. Imperative sentence is commonly finished by the exclamation mark (!). The form of imperative sentence is classified into five, such as imperative without subject, imperative with subject, imperative with let,

negative imperative, and imperative with do. These types of sentence can be found in English written text or conversation according to the kinds of message.

Game has various kind of gameplay it has Single player/Campaign/Story mode gameplay and multiplayer gameplay. Game has not only one genre it has many genres such as action, horror, thriller, and many more. Story mode is version of a computer game in which the player controls a character in a story (dictionary Cambridge.org) therefore there will be conversation between not playable character or NPC and player this will help the researcher to acquire the data.

In this study, the part that were emphasized is the classification of imperative sentence in “Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign” as well as analyzes the constituent structure by using tree diagram.

There are similar studies related with imperative sentence that had been conducted by several other researchers who are namely, Muhammand Fajri (2020), IGA Vina Widiadnya Putri, I Dewa Ayu Devi Maharani Santika, Putu Subaktiasih (2018), Novi Yuniarsi, Supriadin, Rahmawati (2019), Silvia Erlin, Nike Andayani (2015), Tommi Juniarta (2016). The difference of the previous studies and the current study lies in the data source in which spesifically, the data of the current study were taken from *Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign*. Therefore, in order to achieve deeper understanding regarding to the situation where command are created by speaker in conversation and also to avoid misunderstanding, further analysis regarding to imperative sentence is conducted with *Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign* chosen as the data source.

Method

The data was taken from “Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign”. “Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign” is used as the data source because the game provides many imperative sentences especially in military term that support as the data source of this study. Aside of winning best audio design award the game also has an interesting story based in modern era. since it has intense situation on the warzone, the phenomenon of imperative sentence could occur in the dialogue of the characters The data were collected by using documentation method After the data collected, the data were analyzed by using qualitative method and presented descriptively based on the theory proposed by Quirk et al. (1985) for the types of imperative sentence and theory proposed Brown and Miller (1991) to determine the constituent structure of imperative sentence by using tree diagram explanation of the data using descriptive words. Finally, the data regarding to imperative sentence that have been obtained from the game are presented by using both, formal and informal method.

Result and Discussion

Result

After analyzing the data, there are 401 data of imperative sentence found in “Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign”. The imperative sentence can be classified into five types based on the theory proposed by Quirk et al. (1985) such as imperative without subject, imperative with subject, imperative with let, negative imperative and imperative with do. However, in this study only two types found, namely imperative without subject and negative imperative. The finding could be seen in the following table below:

No.	Types of Imperative Sentence	Occurrence	Percentage
1.	Imperative without subject	272	67.83%
2.	Imperative with subject	58	14.46%
3.	Imperative with let	42	10.47%
4.	Negative imperative	29	7.23%
Total Data		401	100%

Based on the table 3.1 shows that the types of imperative sentence in “Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign”. The amount of imperative sentence found was 401 data. The higher type of imperative sentence was the one without subject about 272 data or 67.83% and the second one was imperative with subject with 58 data or 14.46%. the third one was imperative with let 42 data or 10.47%. and least one was Negative imperative 29 data or 7.23%

Discussion

In this section, the imperative sentence in “Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign” was presented in this discussion. There were two component parts were analyzed such as classification of the types of imperative sentence based on the theory proposed by Quirk et al. (1985) and analyzing the constituent structure by using tree diagram based on the theory proposed by Brown and Miller (1991).

The difference between this study and other articles (Muhammand Fajri, 2020), (IGA Vina Widiadnya Putri, I Dewa Ayu Devi Maharani Santika, Putu Subaktiasih, 2018), (Novi Yuniarsi, Supriadin, Rahmawati, 2019), (Silvia Erlin, Nike Andayani 2015), is their articles only focus with the function of imperative sentence and all of the other article using theory by Swan (1982), Hall (1993), and Azar (2003) to distinguished the function of imperative sentence and the other article only have two types of imperative sentence such as positive imperative sentence and negative imperative sentence in other hand (Tommi Juniarta 2016) article was focusing on the types of imperative sentence using theory proposed by Quirk et al (1985) but they only focusing on types of imperative and function of imperative while this study was focusing the all of types of imperative sentence by using theory proposed by Quirk et al (1985), and this study also focusing constituent structure determine the constituent structure of imperative sentence by using tree diagram by using the theory proposed by Brown and Miller (1991).

a. Imperative without Subject

Imperative without subject is a sentence begins with verb and generally has no subject. In this study, there were 272 imperatives without subject found but only 3 data were analyzed as the representative data. The analysis can be explained as follows:

Data 1

“Get up there!” (07.01)

The Data shows that the sentence is classified as imperative without subject since no subject being mentioned in the sentence. The sentence begins with a verb base form. The analysis of constituent structure of imperative sentence shown by tree diagram below:

From the tree diagram above it shows the imperative sentence above described by two phrases such as by noun phrase (NP) and verb phrase (VP). The constituent of NP is derived by zero constituent (Ø) in the beginning. It is proved that the type of the imperative sentence above is imperative without subject. The constituents of VP are derived into V “get” and part “up” while the constituent of NP is symbolized by N “there!”

Data 2

“Help me lift this!” (2.01.11)

Based on the Data, the sentence can categorize as imperative sentence without subject. It can be proved that there is no subject implied in the sentence and has verb base form “Help”. The analysis of constituent structure of imperative sentence is shown by tree diagram below:

From the tree diagram above, the symbol of S on the top as a mother which is divided into two branches namely noun phrase (NP) as left daughter and verb phrase (VP) as the right daughter. The constituent of noun phrase (NP) is symbolized by zero constituent (Ø). It is proved that there is no subject being mentioned. The constituent of verb phrase (VP) are the symbol of verb (V) is “Help”, noun phrase (NP), and verb phrase (VP). The constituent structure of noun phrase (NP) are symbols of pronoun (Pro) “me” and Det “this!”, verb phrase (VP) is derived into verb (V) is “lift”.

Data 3

“Drop her” (54.30)

The Data is classified as imperative without subject. The sentence has no subject constructed since the subject is not needed occurred and started by the verb base form “drop”. The analysis of constituent structure of imperative sentence shown by tree diagram below:

Based on the tree diagram above, the initial symbol S is the sentence which has two branches namely noun phrase (NP) and verb phrase (VP). The constituent of noun phrase (NP) is constructed by zero constituent (Ø) since grammatically, the sentence has no subject. Then the constituent of verb phrase (VP) is derived into verb (V) “drop” while the constituent noun phrase (NP) is derived into pronoun (Pro) “her”.

b. Imperative with subject

Imperative with subject is a sentence implied subject before verb and it used second person or third person there were 58 imperatives without subject found but only 3 data were analyzed as the representative data. The analysis can be explained as follows:

Data 4

“Alex get down!” (33.46)

The Data can be categorized as imperative with subject. it can be seen that the sentence has a subject and began with the word “Alex” this can be classified noun and then followed by verb “get”. The analysis of constituent structure of imperative sentence is shown by tree diagram below:

The tree diagram above is started by initial symbol S, this imperative sentence has two phrases to describe that sentence, those are noun phrase (NP) and verb phrase VP. The constituent of noun phrase (NP) is derived into noun (N) "Alex" as a subject in this sentence because this imperative sentence is categorized as Imperative with Subject. The constituent of verb phrase (VP) are derived into verb (V) "get" and particle (Part) "down!" as the complement of the verb

Data 5

“3-1 get up here now!” (52.24)

Based on the Data this sentence is categorized imperative with subject because there is subject in the sentence. In that sentence “3-1” as a subject “3-1” therefore it categorized as noun because that is code name in military. The analysis of constituent structure of imperative sentence is shown by tree diagram below:

The structure of this imperative sentence is described by using tree diagram. As can be seen above, the sentence has two phrases such as noun phrase (NP) and verb phrase (VP). The constituent of noun phrase (NP) is noun (N) symbol of “3-1”. verb phrase (VP) has four constituents which are the symbol of verb (V) “get”, particle (Part) “up” as the complementizer of the verb, adverb phrase (AP) is a optional constituent it derived into adverb (A) “here” and adverb (A) “now!”.

Data 6

”Garrick use the keycard” (1.24.00)

It can be seen from the Data that the sentence has a subject and began with the word “Garrick” which include into the class word noun. The analysis of constituent structure of imperative sentence is shown by tree diagram below:

The structure of this imperative sentence is described by using tree diagram. It can be seen above, the sentence has two phrases such as noun phrase (NP) and verb phrase (VP). the constituent of noun phrase (NP) is symbolized by noun (N) “Garrick”. The constituents of verb phrase (VP) is verb (V) “use” and for the noun phrase (NP) is derived into determiner (Det) “the” and noun (N) “Keycard”

c. Imperative with let

Imperative with let is a sentence usually used for first person and third person. It can be formed by proposing the verb let without followed by a subject before verb. There were 42 data of imperative with let found. In this study, only focus on 2 data of imperative with let that were analyzed, as follows:

Data 7

”Let’s kill him” (2.48.20)

Based on the Data, the imperative above can be categorized as the type of imperative with let because it is begun with the word “Let’s”. The analysis of constituent structure of imperative sentence is shown by tree diagram below:

The sentence has two main phrases two describe the sentence, those are noun phrase (NP) and verb phrase (VP). this type of imperative is a kind of imperative sentence without subject too. The constituent of noun phrase (NP) is symbolized as constituent zero (Ø) because this sentence has no subject. The constituents of verb phrase (VP) are symbolized by verb (V) “let”. For constituent of noun phrase (NP) is derived to Pronoun “us”, verb (V) “kill” and the last constituent for noun phrase (NP) is derived by Pronoun (Pro) “him”.

Data 8

“Let’s get down” (37:10)

Based on the analysis, the imperative sentence above can be categorized as the type of imperative with let because it doesn’t have subject and it is begun with “Let’s”. The analysis of constituent structure of imperative sentence is shown by tree diagram below:

The structure of imperative sentence is described by using tree diagram. The sentence has two phrases such as noun phrase (NP) and verb phrase (VP). the constituent of noun phrase (NP) is symbolized by zero constituent (Ø) appropriate with the explanation that is stated in the theory purpose by Brown & Miller (1991), that you as the subject is omitted. The constituent of verb phrase (VP) has five element such as verb (V), noun phrase (NP), verb (V), particle (Part) and adverb phrase (AP). The symbol of verb (V) “let”, noun phrase (NP) is derived into Pronoun (Pro) “us”, verb (V) is symbolized by “get”, particle (Part) is symbolized by “down” as the complement of the verb and last the adverb phrase AP is symbolized adverb (A) “there”.

d. Negative Imperative

Negative imperative is a sentence which is marked by auxiliary *do not* or *don't* before base form of imperative. There were 29 data of negative imperative found. In this study, only focus on 2 data of the negative imperative that were analysed, as follows:

Data 9

”Don’t move” (33.47)

The sentence above can be categorized as negative imperative. It can be proved by the word “don’t” itself which is form as a negative sentence. The analysis of constituent structure of imperative sentence shown by tree diagram below:

Based on tree diagram above, In the opening of the sentence, there is an omitted symbol form that shows the sentence has no subject. The sentence has two phrases such as noun phrase (NP) and verb phrase (VP). The constituent of noun phrase (NP) is symbolized by constituent zero (Ø) because the subject is omitted. The constituent of verb phrase (VP) are auxiliary (Aux) “do”, negative (Neg) “not”, and verb (V) ”move”.

Data 10

“Don’t scream Stacy” (1.20.42)

The Data is classified as negative imperative since the negative “don’t” inserted before the infinitive form. The analysis of constituent structure of imperative sentence shown by tree diagram below:

From the tree diagram above, the initial symbol S is symbolized as mother and divided into two constituents, they are noun phrase NP as the left daughter and verb phrase VP as the right daughter. the constituent of noun phrase (NP) is symbolized by zero constituent (Ø), because the subject of the sentence is omitted. The constituent of verb phrase (VP) is derived of auxiliary (Aux) “do”, negative (Neg) “not” which gives the negative meaning to sentence, verb (V) is derived into “scream” while noun phrase (NP) is derived into noun (N) “Stacy”.

Conclusion

This study is focused on analyzing the types of imperative sentence that performed by the characters in *Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign*. The finding of the study shows that are 4 types of imperative sentence with the total number of occurrences as many as 401 times. Among those 401 data, there are 272 (67.83%) of imperative without subject of quantity as the

most dominant type of imperative sentence and followed by the imperative with subject 58 (14.46%), there are imperative with let 42 (10.47%) and finally, negative imperative 29 (7.23%) as the least dominant type of imperative sentence. Based on the dominant types of imperative sentence by the characters in *Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign*, it can be concluded that the characters, in *Call of Duty Black Ops 6 Campaign*, using imperative sentence most of the time to command someone in their team.

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